

Experiment Protocol:

Three codes will be provided for three diagrams. The text below contains an explanation of the three provided codes. After presenting the three codes, there will be three activities, one for each diagram.

In the 'Code Examples' combo box, the three codes are present, named as Code 1, Code 2, and Code 3.

Code 1: Class Diagram.

There are five classes:

- Person
- IndividualPerson
- LegalEntityPerson
- CommonAccount
- Transaction

The class Person has the following attributes:

- personName of type string.
- personIncome of type integer.
- personAccount of type list of accounts.

The classes IndividualPerson and LegalEntityPerson inherit from the class Person.

The class IndividualPerson has the following attribute:

- personCPF of type integer.

The class IndividualPerson has the following method:

- validateCPF

The class LegalEntityPerson has the following attribute:

- personCNPJ of type integer.

The class LegalEntityPerson has the following method:

- validateCNPJ

The class CommonAccount has the following attributes:

- accountNumber of type integer.
- accountPassword of type integer.
- accountTransactions of type list of transactions.

The class CommonAccount has the following methods:

- depositAmount
- validatePassword
- withdrawAmount

The class Transaction has the following attributes:

- transactionType of type integer.
- transactionAmount of type double.

The classes Person and CommonAccount have a one-to-many aggregation relationship because the class Person has a list of CommonAccount objects as one of its attributes.

The classes CommonAccount and Transaction also have a one-to-many aggregation relationship because the class CommonAccount has a list of Transaction objects as one of its attributes.

To generate the class diagram, select the Class Diagram button in the interface or use the shortcut Alt + 2.

Code 2: Use Case Diagram.

For the use case diagram, one more function has been added to the classes IndividualPerson and LegalEntityPerson. These functions are named consultCPF and consultCNPJ, respectively.

A decorator @usecase (at usecase) was used on the lines preceding the following functions to indicate that they are use cases:

- validateCPF
- consultCPF
- validateCNPJ
- consultCNPJ

To generate the use case diagram, select the Use Case Diagram button in the interface or use the shortcut Alt + 3.

Code 3: Entity-Relationship Diagram.

For the entity-relationship diagram, two new attributes were created at the beginning of the class, outside the constructor, to mark them as key attributes:

- accountId in the class CommonAccount as an integer.
- personId in the class Person as an integer.

Two decorators @relationship (at relationship) were used to create a relationship between the classes CommonAccount and Transaction.

The decorators were added to the methods depositAmount and withdrawAmount, and they receive as a parameter, in brackets after the @relationship decorator, the name of the class

they relate to. In this case, the class Transaction was added within the brackets to create the relationship between the classes.

To generate the entity-relationship diagram, select the Entity-Relationship Diagram button in the interface or use the shortcut Alt + 4.

Activities:

Below we have three activities that should be done using Code 3 as a base. At the end of the activity, save the code to be placed in the form at the end of the document.

Activity 1: Class Diagram

For this activity, you need to:

- Create two new classes, SpecialAccount and SavingsAccount, that inherit from the CommonAccount class.
- Add the following attribute to SpecialAccount: accountLimit
- Add the following attribute to SavingsAccount: accountAnniversary

Activity 2: Use Case Diagram

For this activity, you need to:

- Create a new function in the CommonAccount class called updatePassword.
- Mark this new function as a use case using the @usecase (at usecase) decorator.

Activity 3: Entity-Relationship Diagram

For this activity, you need to:

- Create a primary key for the Transaction class called transactionId.
- Create a new function in the Person class called accessAccount.
- Create a relationship in the accessAccount function using the @relationship (at relationship) decorator for the CommonAccount class.

After completing the three activities, save the code to be submitted in the following form: [Experiment Form](#).